

SI Table S2: Sequences of steroidogenesis from plants without available genomes. Transcripts from the following NCBI bioprojects were analysed for species without available genome sequences.

***Allium schoenoprasum* (PRJEB55612 and PRJNA847160):**

SCCE:

>*Allium schoenoprasum* TRINITY_DN5701_c1_g1_i8:211-1638
MAHYIAICSLSILIIWLIKLFQRWRNPRCNGKLPGLGFPPLGETFQFFAPSTTFDIHPFVKERM
NRYGPIFKTSLVGRPIIVSTDHELNNFVQEQGKLFQSWYPDTFTEIFGRNNV GELHGFLYKYL
KSLVLKLFGPESLKERLLSDIEKSACINLRTWSLQPSVDLKEGIATMIFDLTAKKLISYDPSTSSE
NLRHNFVAFIKGLISFPVNIPTGAYNKCLQGRRKAMRVLKQMLAERKSRPNRQCNDFFDYVV
EELKKERPVLTESVALDLMFVLLFASFETTSLALTLAIKLIADHPKVLEGLTEEHEAIRNREDP
ESEITWQEYKSMFTLQVINETARLANIVPGIFRKVLKEIHVNEYTIPAGWGMVCPPAVHLN
SEIFEDPLSFNPWRWKNKAELNGGSKNFMAFGGMRFCVGTDFTKLQMAVFIHCLVTKYRW
KMIKGGNIIRTPGLGFPDGYHVVELLSKE*

3 β -HSD:

>*Allium schoenoprasum* TRINITY_DN12050_c1_g2_i1:72-896
MSKLRLEGKVAIITGAASGIGETS AELFVANGAIVVIADIQDELGQRVAHRINVSSAFKGEDRC
TYGHCDVTDEKQVQDVTDCIATYGRLDIVYSNAGILGSPNTIADLDLAELNRIMTVNVGGA
LAIKHGARAMIAKGIRGSILCTASVAAQRAGLGPVAYTTSKHALLGLVRAAAGEYGPYRIRV
NCVSPFGVATPLSCGLDGVPDVVESIVESVATLKGVRLKTYHVAEALFLVSDQSA YISGHD
LVVDGATTTCCSSSKFGMSSDVA*

KSI:

>*Allium schoenoprasum* TRINITY_DN25223_c0_g1_i2:417-1589
MSGKEMLQAGRVDQVNINGTCNILDVCHDVGVKRLVYVSTYNNVFGGKEIINGNESLPYFPL
DEHVDNYGRSKSVAEQLVLKCNRPSSKKNNGVRLYTCAIRPAAIYGPGEEHRLPRILDLAKM
GLLSFKVGD SHVKT DWVYVDNLVLSLILASMGLLDDIPGRTHPIAAGQAYFICDGSPVNTFDF
IIGPLLKNLEYGLPSITLDVNHAF TLSRVISAFYTL LYPWLNRRWLPNPLLLPAEVYKIGVTHYF
SYLKAREELGYFPMVTPQEGLSKTISYWKERKKEELEGPTLLTWCLVISGMSALFAAAYLPPV
GLLKYLQAIALFMFRSLWLTRLVFVTA VAVHVVEGIYAWFLARRVDPKNSCGWLWQTV AL
GIFSLRFLK RANIM*

Steroid 5 α -reductase:

>*Allium schoenoprasum* TRINITY_DN30024_c0_g1_i11:58-825
MEDYSLYTAALKTLYISAVINVISLPFISAPYGKHFRGGWGPTIPASLAWFLMESPTIFLTICFYP
FGRHVHPLSLLL VFLYLFHYCNRTL VFPQRLRKGA KGFVSVAAAMAFVFNLLNAYVQTRSL
SHYSVYEERLSIWVMVRVLIGVMVFAWGMWVNVQSDLALLRLKKESGGVYKIPRGGWFEY
VCNPNYMGEAAEWFGWAVVAWSPTAWGFFFYTC SNLVPRARANLRWYREKFGEEYPKSM
KAILPFLF*

Steroid 5 β -reductase/ PRISE:

>*Allium schoenoprasum* TRINITY_DN13856_c0_g1_i2:c1642-455
MSWWWAGAIGAARKTL DSSSSSNPNSLPPPQSIALVVGATGIVGTSLLDILPLPDTPGGPWKL
YAVSRRLVSDNPRHPIQCDVSDSSQTLDRLSPLSDVTHIFYVAWANCSSQAQLKVNSSML
RNVLNAVLPNAPNLQHICLLTGRKH YIGAFEFIDKVKPHDPPFYEEMPRLESPNFYD MEDILF
EELEKKDGKVSWSVHRPTTIFGFSSRAAMNVVQGVCVYAAMCKKEKVMRWPGSKVTWD
GFSDASDADLVAEHQIWA AVDPYAKNEAFNCSNGDVFKWKQLWKALAEQFEVEWVGYQG
EDTRFSLKEEMKGKEKVWEEVVKENELVETKLEEVGNWWFLDSVLGIDFAHLDSMNKSKEH
GFLGFRNTLNSFN SWVDKMKAFKIVP*

***Borago officinalis* (PRJEB50033):**

SCCE: not detected!

3 β -HSD:

>*Borago officinalis* TRINITY_DN148989_c0_g1_i1:37-843

MKIYFDFRLEGKVALITGAASGIGEETVRLFAEQGAYVVGADIQDELGQQVIESIGSDKVSYH
HCDVRDENQVEQTVKYTLQKYGDLNILFSNAGIMGPLSSILELNLSEFDDTLATNVRGVVATI
KHVGKAMVERKTKGSIVCTASVSACMGGTGPAYTTSKHALIGLIRTACGELGNYGIRVNSIS
PYGVATPLACNSYHLEPAQVEENSCATANLKGVVLPKPHIAEAALFLASDESGYISGHNLVV
DGGFTVFNQSLSKFQEV*

KSI:

>*Borago officinalis* TRINITY_DN50257_c0_g1_i2:514-1698

MSGKEMLQYGRVDQVNINGTCHVIDACIEKGVGRLVYVSTYNNVFGGKEITNGNESLPYFPI
DDHVDPYGRSKAIAEQLVLKSSGRPFKKKSGCLYTCAIRPAAIYGPEERHLPRIINLAKDLL
PFKIGGPNVKTDWVYVDNLVLALILASMGLLDDIPGKEGKPVASGQPYFISDGSPVNTFEFLR
PILKSLDYDLPKTTVKVSNALLGNFFWGLYSLMYPLLSKTLWLPQPLLLPAEVYKVGVTYHYF
SYLKAKEELGYIPIVSSREGTAATISYWQERKSSTQGSIYTWLFFVAGMLWVFAASYLPDIGP
APFLRAVALFVFRSMWLLQRVFILSAAAHIGEGIYAWILARKVDPENATGFWFWQTFALGIFSL
RYLLKKRKLKAQVDQN*

Steroid 5 α -reductase:

>*Borago officinalis* TRINITY_DN6153_c0_g1_i9:c1186-425

MISDKTLFNYAILTYLSTPPTIISLLFLTAPYGKHRRSGWGPDIAPLAWFFMEAPTLWLTFLL
FPFGQNYTNSKSFILISPFLFHYLNRTIIPYPIKNSANRFPLSVALMAFVFNLLNAYIQARWVSH
YADLREDEWFWRFSGGLVVFIVGMRINVQSDNSLLRLKCQGGGYRIPGGWFEYVSCPNY
FGEVLEWLGYSVMTWSYAGFAFFVYTCANLVPRARANHQWYLDKFGKDYPKNRKCVIPFL
Y*

Steroid 5 β -reductase/ PRISE:

>*Borago officinalis* TRINITY_DN24783_c0_g1_i4:c1787-657_partial

KKLEEDPPTKYQSVGLIIGVTGIIGNSLAEILPLSDTPGGPWKVYGVARRPRPSWNIDHPIEYI
QCDILDKEDCQNKLSKLTVDVTHLFYVTWANGSNPENCQLNGKMFRNLVDVIPNCPNLSHI
CLQTGRKHAGPFESMGKVAHDPPFYEDLARLDVPNYYYVLEDILFSEVEKKEKLTWSVHRP
GSIFGFSPYSMMNIVGGLCVYAAVCKYMNLPLRFPGCKEAWDGYSDCSDADLVAEHQIWA
VDPYAKNEAFNVSNGDVFKWKHFWRVLAEQFGVECADFEEGTSKFSLKEMMKDKAGVWE
EIVEANGLVATKLEEVGCWWYIDLVLGIAPMLDTMNKSKEHGFLGFRNSKNAFISWIDKVKV
HKIVP*

***Myosotis sylvatica* (PRJNA451174):**

SCCE:

>*Myosotis sylvatica* TRINITY_DN45926_c0_g1_i2:c1246-329_partial
EKYGSIFRTSIVGRPVIVSADSDLNYYIFQQEQLFQSWYPDTFTEIFGKQNVGSLHGFMYKYH
IFVELKDSTARMIFDLTAKKLISYDSEKSSENLRENFVAFIQGLISFPLDVPGTAYHKCMQGRK
KAMKMLKNLLQERRANPRKEQTDFFDYVVQELKREDTVLTEAIALDLMFVLLFASFETTSLA
ITLAVKFLSENPLVLRQLTEEHEAIIRKRENPDSGVTWQEYKSMFTTFQFINETVRLANIVPAIF
RKTLRDIKFKGYTIPAGWAVMVCPPAVHLNPARYTNPLEFNPCRWEGVELHGVSKNFMAFG
GGMRFCVGTDFTKVQMAVFLHSLVTKYKWKLRGGQTVRTPGLQFPEGMHIVTKKDRDAP
AE

3 β -HSD:

>*Myosotis sylvatica* TRINITY_DN7591_c0_g1_i2:69-857
MSKLRLEGKVALITGGASGIGEETVRLFVEEGAFVVAADIQDELGQQLIQSISSDKVSYHHCD
VRDEKQVEETVNYTVQKYGELNVLFNSAGIIGPLTSILELNLSEFDDTIATNVRGVLATIKHAG
RAMVERKTKGSIVVTASVAACVGGTGPAYTTSKHALIGLIRTACGELGNYGIRVNSISPYGV
ATPLTCKAYHLEASDVEENSCATANLKGVLKATHVAETALFLASDQSAYVSGHNLVVDGG
FTVFNQSLSKY*

KSI:

>*Myosotis sylvatica* TRINITY_DN1104_c0_g1_i3:452-1606
MLQYGRVDEVNINGTCHVIDACVEKGARRLVYVSTYNVVFVGGKEITNGNESLPYFPISDHVD
PYGRSKSIAEQLVLKSNRPFKKGDCLYTCAIRPAAIYGPEERHLPRIVNLAKLGILPFTVG
EPHVKTDWVYVDNLVLSLILASMGLLDDIPGKEGKPVASGQPYFISDGSPVNSFEFLRPILNSL
DYDLPKRTLTVSHALLGNFFWALYSLMYPWLRKTWLPQPLMLPAEVYKVGVTHTYFSYLKA
KEELGYTPMVSPREGMAATISYWQERKSSVQGPTIYNWLFVVGMLWVFAAFLPDIGPVPF
LRAVGLFFFRSIGALQTLFILAAAHAIGEAIYAWKLAKKIDPANATSWFWQTFALGFFSLRFL
KKRKSIV*

Steroid 5 α -reductase:

>*Myosotis sylvatica* TRINITY_DN23071_c0_g3_i1:92-865
MFSEQTFFNYALLSIYLITPPTIISLRFLTAPYGKHHHRAGWGNIPAPLAWLLMESPTLWLTYYL
FPLGRNQPNPKARLLIAPFLLHYLHRTLLYPLRLLRRGGPSNAFPVSVLLAFANLLNSYLQ
ARWVSHYADFDTDHWFVPRFVLGLGVFGAGMWINVKCDNELLALKSKGGGYRIPRGGLFE
YVSCPNYFGEVLEWFGWAVMTCSFVGFAFFAYTCANLVPRARDNHKWYKKGEDYPENR
KCIIPFIY*

Steroid 5 β -reductase/ PRISE:

>*Myosotis sylvatica* TRINITY_DN40999_c0_g1_i1:385-1554
MSWWWGAIGAANKKFEDEQPTKYESVGLIIGVTGIVGNSLAEILPLSDTPGGPWKVYGVVA
RRRPSWNADHPIEYIQCDILDKEDCQSKLSKLVDTVHLFYVTWANKSTESENCEVNGKMR
NLLDVVIPNCPNLQHICLQTRKHYLGPFESMDKVAHDPPYEDLPRLDVVPNFYVLEDILFS
EVEKKEKLTWSVHRPGHIFGFSYMMNIVGTLCVYATICKHMNLPFRFPGCKEAWEGYADC
SDADLIAEHIIWAAVDPYAKNEAFNVSNGDVFKWKHFWRVLAEQFGVECAEFEEGEQKLSL
QELMKDKAVVWDEIVEANGLLATELGEVATWWFVDLVGLIPQTLDTMNSKEHGFLGFRNS
KNAFISWIDKVKVHKVVP*

***Plantago lanceolata* (PRJNA636383):**

SCCE:

>*Plantago lanceolata* TRINITY_DN21777_c0_g1_i1:1-954_partial
YKYFKNMVLSLFGPESLKRMITDVENQSRFTLQNWSNPNPSVELKDGIKMFGLTAKKLISCD
SEESCDNLRKNFVDFVDGLISFPLNFPGTAYYRCLQGRKKAMKTLKNMFQERRKTPQAIQSD
FFDYVLEELEKKDTILTEAIALDLMFVLLFASYETASLATTMATKFLADNPLALQKLTEEHETI
VNLREDPDSGLTWKEYKSMTFTFQVINETLRLANIAPGIFRKAMVDTKFKEYTIPAGWSVMV
CPPAVHLDPPKYPNPLDFNPWRWDGLDTSVGSRNFMFAFGGGMRLCIGADFTKVQMAVFLH
CLVTKYK*

3 β -HSD:

>*Plantago lanceolata* TRINITY_DN61292_c0_g1_i1:c1004-105
MTAQVLPESFAGIQFLNKDMCSPHHPIKRLEGKVAIITGGARGIGEATVKVFASQGARVVIA
DVEDMLGNSLAQSLGPNVTFVHCDVTSEEDIENVVTSTVSKYKIDILFNNAGVLGDQSKHK
SILDFDADEFDRIMRVNVRGAMLGIKHVARAMIRYGGGGCVISTASVAGVMGGLGPHSYTAS
KHAIVGMTKNAACELGRYGIRVNCISPFVATKMLVDAWRVGGDNGSAGVTESEVEKIEEF
VRGLGNLKGTELRTKDIAEAALFLASDESRYISGHNLVVDGGVTTSKNCVGL*

KSI:

>*Plantago lanceolata* TRINITY_DN3786_c0_g1_i27:5-1306_partial
RPDSPWSDDLNRNRGVRCLQGDVARKEDVEKALRGADCVFHLASYGMSGKEMLRYSRVDEV
NINGTCHILDACLTYGIGRLVYVSTYNVIFGGKEIVNGNESLPYFPLDNHEDPYGRSKSIAEQL
VLKSNGKPFKKKQGKLYTCAIRPAAIYGPEERHLPRIMNLAKLGLLPFKIGSRNVKSDWVY
VDNLVLSLLLASMGLSDDIPGRVGGQPIAAGQPYFISDGPVNSFEFLQPLLKSFYDLPQSSLA
VPHALFLGKVFVWAIYSLVYPWLRQRWIPQPLILPAEVYKVGVTHTYFSFLKAREELHYAPMVS
PQEGMNATIEYWKERKRNEIDGPTIYAWLFVIIGMTMLFCAACMPDVGPFHLCRAIYLFRRS
MLTVRILFFSSVAAHIGEGVYAWQLAKKADPANAKGWFQTAAMGYFSLRFLKAKK*

Steroid 5 α -reductase:

>*Plantago lanceolata* TRINITY_DN35496_c0_g1_i1:139-951
MVFSDEQIYHYALLTLYLITPLTFLSLQFLTAPYKGKHNRPGWGPTIPPPIAWCLMESPTVFLSLL
LFPRGRNHLNPRAYLLISFLLHYLHRTFIYPLRLFLKSISPNSPKPGSVNPGSVKPGFPVSIALT
AFVFNLLNGYLQSRWVSEYAELSDRWFVYRVVGGGAVFLGGMAANIWSDNFLMRLKESG
GGYRVPRGGLFEWVTSPNYFGEIVEWLGWAFMCWSWAGLGFFLYTCANLVPRAASGRKWY
LEKFGEDFPKHKRAVIPFLY*

Steroid 5 β -reductase/ PRISE: Previously published on NCBI (WKF48834.1; Dorfner et al., 2024).

>*Plantago lanceolata* WKF48834.1
MSWWWAGAIGAACKRSEDEDDAPPKHASVALIVGVTGIVGNSLAEILPLADTPGGPWKVYGV
ARRPRPAWNEDNPINYIRCDVSDPEDTKEKLSPLTDITHVFYVTWANRSTESSENCEANGKML
KNVLDVVIPNCPDLKHISLQTGRKHYCGPFELLGKIESHDPPFTEDLPRLKCENFYTTQEDLLF
EEVEKREGLTWSVHRPGNIFGFSPYSMMNLVGTLCVYAAICKHEGKVLRFPGCKAAWDGYS
DCSDADLIAEHHIWAAVDPYAKNEAFNVSNVDVFKWKHFWKVLAEQFGVECGEYEEGEDL
KLQDLMKGKEPVWEEIVRENALSPTNLEDVGVWWFSDLILGFPCPLDSMNSKHEHGFLGFRN
SKNSLISWIDKAKAYKIVP*

***Pelargonium zonale* (PRJNA807121):**

SCCE:

>*Pelargonium zonale* TRINITY_DN19848_c0_g1_i38:c1744-299
MLTLQVQQYVVCFVGVVVAGISVWYKWANPKCNGKLPFGSMGFPPFFGETFEFFTPHHFYGI
PPFVVRKRISRYGSVFRVTSLVGRKVVVSTDPEINYSIFQQEGKSFLIWTESFIKILGQQSMLAYH
GIVHKYLKLNILHLVSPENLREKLLLEMDSATRRHLQSWATHGSVDVKEATSTMIFEYFSKLL
MSYDEPRALENLKNNYNFIDGLISFPLNIPGTAYHACLKGRQNAVVKVIKDFRERKRSKIRYN
DFLDHLLLEEMEKEGSILDEAIAIDL VVLLFATYETTSAAITLLTKFISEHQEVVAELMREHDAI
VRSRDQDKDSEVTWKEYKSMTFTHMVINETVRLANIVPGIFRKVKDVEIKGYTIPAGWVV
MIVPSVVHLNPKFEDPLAFNPWRWQGGQELHAGSKSFMAFGGGLRLCVGADFAKLQMALFL
HLLTKYRWTVTKGGDITRRPGLVFPTGFHVEIQHKTPIA*

3 β -HSD:

>*Pelargonium zonale* TRINITY_DN15032_c0_g1_i1:c910-128
MSTPRLQGKVAIVTGGASGIGEEAARLFCENGAFVVVADVQDELGQSVVASINSKSADRASY
HHCDVRDEKQVEETVSFAVQKYGTLDVMFSNAGIYGPAFGIMEVDLELFDNTMATNVRGVA
ATIKHAARAMVAKKVRGGSIICTASVAASVGGMGPSAYTASKHAVVGLVRAACAELGAHGI
RVNVCVSPFGVATPLACTAVNLEASELESGETSALANLKGIVLKARHIAEAALFLASDDSAYTSG
LNLNVDGGFTVVR*

KSI:

>*Pelargonium zonale* TRINITY_DN2732_c1_g1_i3:c1458-274
MSGKEMLQFGRVDEVNINGTCHVLEACLEFEIKRLVYVSSYNVVFVGGKEIVNGNESLPYFPID
DHVDSYGRSXSIAEQLVLKSNRPFKKDTGKCLYTCAVRPAAIYGPGEERHLPRIISLAKLGLL
PFKIGEQSVMQDWIYVDNLILALILASMGLLDDIPGRPKHPVAAGQAYFVSDGSPVNTFEFIRP
LLRSLDYELPKPSLTIHQALILGKFFEVYTYLIPWLNRRWLPQPFLPAEVYKVGVTHTYFSFL
KAREELGYVPMVTPQEGMAATVAYWQERRLKTVDGPTIYVWLFCVFGMFQLFCGAFLPPVG
PVRLLRRAISLFFFRSLWIVRLVFILAAGAHIGESLYAWRLAKRVDPENSVRWFVWQTFALGFFSL
RFLKAKQYKRVE*

Steroid 5 α -reductase:

>*Pelargonium zonale* TRINITY_DN2186_c2_g1_i2:43-663_partial
AWFLMESPTLWLSLLLLKHPLNPRSLLLFSPFLHYLNRTILFPIRLLRLNRNRRSPNFPASIAA
MAFAYNVLNSYVQARSVFEFGDYSDRWFWWRFGAGLVVFSGGMAVNVWADSVLVRLLR
EGGGYRVPIGGWFEVVSCPNYFGEIVEWFGWAVMCGSWAGFGFFVYTCANLVPRARANHR
WYLEKFGEDYPKKRKAVIPFLY

Steroid 5 β -reductase/ PRISE:

>*Pelargonium zonale* TRINITY_DN701_c2_g1_i1:294-1469
MSWWWAGAIGAACKKFDDEAQLPRTFQSTALVVGVTGIVGNSLAEILPLSDTPGGLWKVY
GVARRPRPNWNADHPYEQCDVSDPQDSQSKLSTLTDVTHVFYVAWANRSTEAENCKVNS
DMFRNVLRVIPNAPNLRHVCLQTGKHYIGSFESFGRSQPHDPPFTEDIPRLSGPNFYDLED
VMFQEVAKKEGLTWSVHRPDLIFGFSPYSLMNIVGTAVYAAICKHEGTPLWFPGSKAAWES
YQVASDADLVAEQHIWAAVDPYARDEAFNCNNGDVFRWKQFWKVLAEQFGVEKHGFEEG
KNVKLSEMMKDKGHVWEEIVRVNQLQPTKLEEVGVWWFADTVLGGEGMLSSMNKSKEHG
FVGFRNSKNSFVSWIDKVKSFKIVP*

Ribes rubrum (PRJNA1131118):

SCCE: not detected!

3 β -HSD:

>*Ribes rubrum* TRINITY_DN197036_c0_g1_i1:c874-92

MSKPRLEGKVAITGAASGIGEETVRLFVENGAFVVVADVQDELGRKVVASIGSEKVAFHHC
DVRDEKQVEETINFTIEKYGTLDVLFNSAGVMGPLTGILDLDLNEYDNTMTTNVIRGVAATIK
HASRAMVARKTRGSIICTASVAGSIGGAGPLGYTTSKHALVGLVRSACSELGKYGIRVNCISPF
GIATPLSCIA YDLKPSEVENNSCDLANLKGIVLKPKHVSQAAVFLASYESAYISGHNLALDGGF
TVVNHSTF*

KSI:

>*Ribes rubrum* TRINITY_DN1856_c0_g1_i4:c1494-328

MSGKEMLQFGRVDEVSINGTCHILDACVEFGIKRLVYVSTYNNVFGGKEIVSGNETLPYFPLD
DHVDPYGRSKSVAEQLVLKSNRPTKEKGGKCVYTCAIRPGAIYGPGEERHLPRIVSLAKLGLI
PFRIGEANVKTDWVFDNLVLGLILASMGLLDNIPGKGGKHPAAAGQPYFISDGSPVNSIEFLRP
LLTSLDYDLPKASITVPHALVLGRIFSAIYTILYPWLNRRWWLPQPLILPAEIYKVGVTHTYFSYL
KAKEELGYIPMVTREGMASTISYWQERKRRMLDGPITYTWLFCVIGMTSLFAVAACLPDFVP
VPLFRSLSLFIFRSIWTVRLFLFAAAAHIGEAFYAWHLAKRVPANKRGWFWQTFALGIFSL
RLLLKRARK*

Steroid 5 α -reductase:

>*Ribes rubrum* TRINITY_DN6274_c0_g1_i8:415-1182

MDSDQTLFHYSLLTLYITAPPTYISLRFLQAPYGKHHRPGWGPMTSPPLAWFLMESPTVWLTL
FLFPLGRHSSNPKALILPFLIHYLHRTILYPIRLTRRKTTSFGFPVSIALMACGFNLLNSYLQAR
WVSHYNDYEGVGVFWWRVIGLVVSVSGMAVNIWSDSVLVGLKSGGGGYKVPKGGWFEM
VSCPNYFGEILEWLGWAVMTWSWAGFGFFLYTCANLVPRARANHQWYLEKFKEDYPKGRK
AVIPFLY*

Steroid 5 β -reductase/ PRISE:

>*Ribes rubrum* TRINITY_DN313_c0_g1_i33:c1382-210

MNWWWAGAIGAAKKKSEEDEAPRSYQSVALIIGVTGVVGNLAEILPLSDTPGGLWKVYGV
ARRERPWNADHPIEYIQCDVSDPEDTMAKLSPLTDVTHIFYVTWTNRLTEIENCKANGAMF
RNVLAAVIPSALDLRHICLQTGTHYMGPFDSLKGIQPHDPPFTEDLPRLEVNFYTTLEDILF
ETAEKKEELTWSVHRPQAIKGFSPYSMMNIIGTLCVYAAICKHEGKPLKFPGVKSAWECYSTA
SDADLIAEHIIWAAVDPYAKNEAFNCSNGDVFKWKHLWKVLAEQFGIECVFEDENEPRVTL
QELMKGKEAVWDEIVKENELQPTKLEEVGLWWLSDLVFSGEALLDSMNKSKEHGFLGFRNS
KNSLITWIDKMKAYKIVP*

References:

Dorfner M, Klein J, Senkleiter K, Lanig H, Kreis W, Munkert J. 2024. Addressing the Evolution of Cardenolide Formation in Iridoid-Synthesizing Plants: Site-Directed Mutagenesis of PRISEs (Progesterone-5 β -Reductase/Iridoid Synthase-like Enzymes) of *Plantago* Species. *Molecules* **29**: 5788.